

Considerations on Particle Shifting Technique for SPH schemes

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Abstract—This paper addresses the Particle Shifting Technique (PST) in the SPH schemes. Improving the accuracy of SPH schemes leads to particle clustering along the flow streamlines which turns to be detrimental for the simulations. PSTs aim at avoiding this adverse effect by slightly disordering the particles, allowing to retrieve a regular particle distribution within the kernel interpolation support. The gain in accuracy is such that this technique is now commonly adopted by the SPH practitioners, however the conditions that should be respected by a PST are not clearly discussed in the literature. In this paper, such conditions are exposed and their fulfillment by the main existing PSTs of the literature is analyzed. None of these existing PSTs fully satisfying these conditions, a novel PST is introduced. The proposed PST is validated for three different SPH schemes in 2D.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) method suffers from the presence of anisotropic particle structures inherent to its Lagrangian feature [10], [6], [12]. While this effect appears when improving the scheme accuracy, it tends paradoxically to degrade the kernel interpolation due to the irregular particle distribution obtained within the compact support. The Particle Shifting Technique (PST) sounds as a suitable tool to remedy this problem as it is increasingly discussed in the SPH literature [10], [18], [6], [12], [5], [15]. The principle of the PST is to move slightly the particles from their Lagrangian trajectories in order to recover a regular particle distribution in space. This is achieved by adding a small perturbation δu within the velocity field [10], [12], [15] or by introducing a modification δr in the particle positions [6], [5].

The first PST was introduced by Monaghan [10] in the compressible SPH context in order to avoid particle clustering. The PST velocity δu introduced in that paper was Galilean invariant. In [6], a new PST was introduced within the projection-based Incompressible SPH (ISPH) formalism, compatible with the presence of a free-surface. It was achieved by using a PST displacement δr based on Fick's law, providing a shifting of the particles from areas of high concentration to those of low concentration. Since the introduction of a PST based on Fick's law, various adaptations have been performed for different SPH schemes: (i) using Arbitrary Lagrangian Eulerian (ALE) formalism by Oger *et al.* [12], (ii) using δ -stabilization term by Sun *et al.* [16], [15], (iii) in the ISPH context by Khayyer *et al.* [5], (iv) in another context to initialize correctly an SPH simulation using the particle packing algorithm derived by Colagrossi *et al.* [4]. Although these PSTs have been validated through various challenging test cases, the conditions that should be respected by a PST have not been addressed clearly in the SPH literature.

This paper aims at proposing a list of conditions that any PST should verify from our point of view, and then to introduce a methodology to build it. To this end, a theoretical study of already existing PSTs is carried out in one dimension, derived from the results obtained by Quinlan *et al.* [14] about the truncation error of SPH operators. Thereafter, a methodology that fulfills these conditions is introduced together with a novel PST law satisfying them.

II. PSTS IN THE SPH LITERATURE

A. Monaghan [10]

The first PST was proposed by Monaghan [10] in order to avoid particle clustering. It reads:

$$\delta \mathbf{u}_i^{MON} = 2\epsilon \sum_{j \in \mathcal{D}_i} V_j \rho_j \left(\frac{\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i}{\rho_i + \rho_j} \right) W_{ij}, \quad (1)$$

where ϵ is a parameter, typically set to $\epsilon = 0.5$. $\delta \mathbf{u}$, \mathbf{u} , ρ and V stand for the PST velocity, the Lagrangian velocity, the density and the volume associated the particles, respectively, while W is the kernel and \mathcal{D}_i the kernel support. This PST has the advantage of being Galilean invariant. However, there is no clear reason for which $\delta \mathbf{u}_i^{MON}$ could point towards zones of low concentration of particles, as it is not derived from Fick's law.

B. PSTs based on Fick's law

Lind *et al.* [6] derived a PST based on Fick's law, using the gradient of the particle concentration ∇C_i . ∇C_i was computed through the approximation of $\nabla 1$ as defined in Eq. (2) (i.e. with $C \equiv 1$) corresponding to a vector pointing towards the zone of high concentration of particles [4]. Therefore, $-\nabla C_i$ is a vector pointing towards zones of low concentration of particles and sounds as a relevant basis of a PST.

$$\nabla C_i = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{D}_i} \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j. \quad (2)$$

Nevertheless, the following modified expression firstly derived by Monaghan [11] to prevent tensile instability was preferred in [6]:

$$\widehat{\nabla} C_i = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{D}_i} \left[1 + 0.2 \left(\frac{W_{ij}}{W(\Delta x_i)} \right)^4 \right] \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, \quad (3)$$

where Δx_i is the characteristic distance between two adjacent particles. To obtain a displacement, the concentration gradient approximation $\widehat{\nabla} C_i$ was then multiplied by $0.5h^2$, with h the smoothing length of the kernel support. However, using $\delta \mathbf{r}_i = -0.5h^2 \widehat{\nabla} C_i$ as it is may lead to a PST displacement higher than the smoothing length. To prevent such strong PST displacements, an upper limit of $0.2h$ was imposed leading finally to:

$$\delta \mathbf{r}_i = \begin{cases} -0.5h^2 \widehat{\nabla} C_i & \text{if } \left\| 0.5h^2 \widehat{\nabla} C_i \right\| < 0.2h \\ -0.2h \frac{\widehat{\nabla} C_i}{\left\| \widehat{\nabla} C_i \right\|} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}.$$

Table I: Summary of existing PST velocities based on Fick's law.

	d^{ch}	U^{ch}	$\widehat{\nabla} C_i$	U^{lim}
Lind <i>et al.</i> [6]	h	$h/\Delta t$	$-\widehat{\nabla} C_i$	$0.2h/\Delta t$
Oger <i>et al.</i> [12]	R	$Ma c_0$	$-\nabla C_i$	$0.25 \ \mathbf{u}_i\ $
Sun <i>et al.</i> [15]	$2h$	$Ma c_0$	$-\widehat{\nabla} C_i$	$0.5 U_{max}$

Although the PST was presented in terms of displacement in [6], note that it can also be rewritten as a velocity term using a time derivation approximation, as:

$$\delta \mathbf{u}_i = \begin{cases} -0.5h \frac{h}{\Delta t} \widehat{\nabla} C_i & \text{if } \left\| 0.5h \frac{h}{\Delta t} \widehat{\nabla} C_i \right\| < 0.2 \frac{h}{\Delta t} \\ -0.2 \frac{h}{\Delta t} \frac{\widehat{\nabla} C_i}{\left\| \widehat{\nabla} C_i \right\|} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases},$$

where Δt denotes the time step.

Since the introduction of such a PST based on Fick's law, various adaptations have been derived, specifically to deal with the weakly-compressible SPH assumption. For example Oger *et al.* [12] derived a PST velocity to study the ALE scheme of Vila [18], while Sun *et al.* [15] used another variant PST velocity to study the δ^+ -SPH scheme. These two PST velocities have been established following the same idea, i.e. (i) choose a vector pointing towards zone of low concentration of particles $\widehat{\nabla} C_i$, (ii) choose a characteristic length d^{ch} linked to the kernel support, (iii) choose a characteristic velocity U^{ch} , (iv) limit the PST velocity amplitude to a certain value U^{lim} . To summarize, these three PST velocities can be written using the following generic formulation:

$$\delta \mathbf{u}_i = \begin{cases} U^{ch} d^{ch} \widehat{\nabla} C_i & \text{if } \left\| U^{ch} d^{ch} \widehat{\nabla} C_i \right\| < U^{lim}, \\ U^{lim} \frac{\widehat{\nabla} C_i}{\left\| \widehat{\nabla} C_i \right\|} & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

with the parameters listed in Tab. I, where R is the kernel support radius, Ma the Mach number, c_0 the nominal sound speed and U_{max} the expected maximum Lagrangian velocity.

It is important to note that (i) the PST velocities of Oger *et al.* and Sun *et al.* are not compatible with the incompressible assumption (presence of c_0) and (ii) the PST velocity derived from Lind *et al.* is expressed differently considering the incompressible or the weakly-compressible assumption,

since Δt is computed using the Lagrangian velocity (incompressible) and the nominal sound speed (weakly-compressible).

III. EXPECTED REQUIREMENTS OF A PST

This section addresses the conditions that should be fulfilled by a PST from our point of view. The first condition is to enforce the PST velocity to tend towards zero while refining the spatial resolution, which stands as a consistency requirement. The second condition is the Galilean invariance of the PST as proposed initially in [10] with the additional local rotation invariance. The third condition is the independence between local PST and global behavior of the fluid flow solution.

A. Consistency of the PST velocity

Unlike other numerical methods such as the Finite Volume method for instance, the SPH equations are consistent to the Euler/Navier-Stokes equations with two convergence criteria: $\Delta x \rightarrow 0$ and $\Delta x/R \rightarrow 0$. Practically, the second criterion is impossible to fulfill as a finite number of neighbor particles is expected within the kernel support. Therefore, SPH simulations are usually performed using a constant $R/\Delta x$ ratio. Thus, as far as the PST is concerned, the first condition that should be imposed is:

$$\lim_{\substack{\Delta x \rightarrow 0 \\ \frac{R}{\Delta x} = cst}} \delta \mathbf{u}_i = \mathbf{0} . \quad (5)$$

This condition is necessary to be consistent with the Euler/Navier-Stokes equations when dealing with an SPH scheme in which the PST is not taken into account in the continuity and momentum equations, like in [10] and [16] for example. This requirement can be theoretically alleviated when using an ALE formalism [18], [12], [3]. Nevertheless, in practice the mass and volume of isolated particles can strongly deviate from their initial values, which causes some adverse consequences on the solution [3]. Thus, condition (5) is suitable for these two families of SPH schemes.

In order to establish the convergence property of a PST velocity written using the generic formulation (4), we start here by studying ∇C_i . From Quinlan *et al.* [14], the truncation error of the gradient of a function A can be estimated in one

dimension using Eq. (6), where ξ is a measure of the disorder within the particle distribution.

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{j \in \mathcal{D}_i} A_j \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j - A'_i = \\ & \frac{A_i}{R} \left[\xi O \left(\left(\frac{\Delta x}{R} \right)^3 \right) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\xi^2 + \frac{1}{12} \right) O \left(\left(\frac{\Delta x}{R} \right)^4 \right) \right] \\ & + A'_i \left[\xi O \left(\left(\frac{\Delta x}{R} \right)^3 \right) + O \left(\left(\frac{\Delta x}{R} \right)^4 \right) \right] \\ & + A'_i R \left[\xi O \left(\frac{\Delta x}{R} \right) + O \left(\left(\frac{\Delta x}{R} \right)^4 \right) \right] + \dots \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

In our case, we are interested in $A \equiv 1$, leading to:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla C_i &= \sum_{j \in \mathcal{D}_i} \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j = \\ & \frac{1}{R} \left[\xi O \left(\left(\frac{\Delta x}{R} \right)^3 \right) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\xi^2 + \frac{1}{12} \right) O \left(\left(\frac{\Delta x}{R} \right)^4 \right) \right] . \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

Then, multiplying ∇C_i by the characteristic length R leads to the following property:

$$R \nabla C_i = O(1) , \quad (8)$$

when considering a fixed ratio $R/\Delta x$. Note that (i) the previous development has been carried out with a characteristic length $d^{ch} = R$, but the result is still valid with all the characteristic lengths d^{ch} of Tab. I, and (ii) using $\widehat{\nabla} C_i$ instead of ∇C_i leads to the same conclusions since in that case, the derivatives of the function A in (6) are such that: $A^{(2k+1)} \equiv 0$ thanks to the symmetry of the kernel and $|A^{(2k)}| \leq C_k/R^{2k}$ where C_k depends on the ratio $R/\Delta x$ and on the choice of the kernel.

Therefore, since the velocities U^{ch} and U^{lim} introduced in Tab. I are $O(1)$, the following conclusions can be drawn for all the PSTs introduced in Tab. I:

- 1) In terms of velocity, $\delta \mathbf{u}_i = O(1)$ and then:

$$\lim_{\substack{\Delta x \rightarrow 0 \\ \frac{R}{\Delta x} = cst}} \delta \mathbf{u}_i \neq \mathbf{0} . \quad (9)$$

- 2) In terms of displacement, $\delta \mathbf{r}_i = O(\Delta x)$ and then:

$$\lim_{\substack{\Delta x \rightarrow 0 \\ \frac{R}{\Delta x} = cst}} \delta \mathbf{r}_i = \mathbf{0} . \quad (10)$$

This property is highlighted numerically in [15].

As a consequence, in order to recover the consistency condition (5) for a PST velocity written in the generic form (4), a relevant choice is to consider a characteristic velocity such that:

$$\lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} U^{char} = 0. \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{R}{\Delta x} = cst$$

B. Uniform translation and local rotation invariance

As already mentioned in Section II-A, the PST introduced by Monaghan has the advantage of being Galilean invariant. This is the second condition that the PST should verify. Moreover, the PST should be the same with or without the presence of rotation at any instant.

The quantity $R\nabla C_i$ (or $R\widehat{\nabla}C_i$) itself is invariant by uniform translation and local rotation. Then, U^{ch} and U^{lim} should be chosen properly so that $\delta\mathbf{u}$ maintains this nice property. Note that using the local or global Lagrangian particle velocity does not allow these invariance conditions to be fulfilled. Conversely, using a relative velocity such that $U_i^{ch} = f(\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i)$ is a sufficient condition.

Furthermore, using a first order Taylor's expansion (at location \mathbf{x}_i for instance), leads theoretically to:

$$\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i \approx \overline{\nabla}\mathbf{u}_{x_i}(\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i) = O(\Delta x), \quad (12)$$

where $\overline{\nabla}\mathbf{u}_{x_i}$ is the velocity gradient at \mathbf{x}_i . Then, basing U_i^{ch} and U_i^{lim} on $\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i$ in the generic PST velocity formulation (4) allows for ensuring both the Galilean invariance and the consistency condition (5) where $\mathbf{u} \in \mathcal{C}^1$, with a theoretical first order convergence rate. In addition, with a projection $(\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \frac{\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i}{\|\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i\|}$, the local rotation invariance is obtained.

To summarize, using the characteristic (and limitation) velocity proposed in (13) in the generic form (4) allows to fulfill (i) the condition of Galilean and local rotation invariance, (ii) the consistency condition (5).

$$U_i^{ch} = \max_{j \in \mathcal{D}_i} \left(\left| (\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \frac{\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i}{\|\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i\|} \right| \right) \quad (13)$$

C. Independence of the PST from the solution

The PST should act with respect to a local measure of the flow dynamics. For example, in a dam-break test case, the maximum Lagrangian velocity is reached in the fluid front, whereas the dynamics of the flow is relatively low elsewhere. In such a case, basing the PST on the maximum Lagrangian velocity U_{max} can lead to an excessive particle shifting in low dynamics region. This last condition proposed aims at avoiding such an undesirable property.

$R\nabla C_i$ (or $R\widehat{\nabla}C_i$) are some local quantities and therefore do not depend on the global behavior of the flow. The characteristic velocity proposed in (13) been independent of any global velocity of the flow, it allows for fulfilling also the desired local property of the PST.

IV. PST ENHANCEMENTS

A. Proposition of an improved PST velocity

From the discussion and analysis drawn in Section III, we derive here the proposition of an enhanced PST, based on the generic form (4), where the characteristic velocity U_i^{ch} is defined in (13), and the coefficient $(R/\Delta x)^3$ is introduced to counterbalance the term of higher degree of (7). Theoretically, $R\widehat{\nabla}C_i$ is $O(1)$ but it is not possible to predict its exact value a priori. To prevent excessive values, a limitation velocity U_i^{lim} is prescribed, also based on (13) with an additional coefficient $\frac{1}{2}R/\Delta x$. Finally, a global coefficient 0.5 is added, leading to the PST velocity (14).

The properties of the proposed PST are summarized in Tab. II. By construction, the proposed PST verifies the targeted conditions introduced in Section III. Furthermore, another advantage of this PST is its compatibility with the incompressible assumption, thanks to the absence of sound speed terms.

B. SPH schemes used to validate the present PST

In this work, the PST is validated through different SPH schemes, which are first recalled in the present section. For all these schemes, the system of equations is closed using the Cole equation of state $p = \frac{c_0^2 \rho_0}{\gamma} \left[\left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \right)^\gamma - 1 \right]$ where γ , ρ_0 and c_0 are respectively the polytropic constant, reference density and nominal speed of sound.

$$\delta \mathbf{u}_i = 0.5 \begin{cases} - \max_{j \in \mathcal{D}_i} \left(\left| (\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \frac{\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i}{\|\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i\|} \right| \right) \left(\frac{R}{\Delta x} \right)^3 R \widehat{\nabla} C_i & \text{if } \left\| \left(\frac{R}{\Delta x} \right)^3 R \widehat{\nabla} C_i \right\| < \frac{1}{2} \frac{R}{\Delta x}, \\ - \max_{j \in \mathcal{D}_i} \left(\left| (\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \frac{\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i}{\|\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i\|} \right| \right) \frac{1}{2} \frac{R}{\Delta x} \frac{\widehat{\nabla} C_i}{\|\widehat{\nabla} C_i\|} & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

Table II: Summary of the theoretical properties of PSTs based on Fick's law.

	$\lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \delta \mathbf{r} = \mathbf{0}$	$\lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \delta \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0}$	Galilean and local rotation invariance	Independence global flow / local PST	Compatibility with incompressible assumption
Lind <i>et al.</i> [6]	Yes	if $\frac{\Delta x}{R} \rightarrow 0$	No	No	Derived for incompressible
Oger <i>et al.</i> [12]	Yes	if $\frac{\Delta x}{R} \rightarrow 0$	No	No	No
Sun <i>et al.</i> [15]	Yes	if $\frac{\Delta x}{R} \rightarrow 0$	No	No	No
Present PST	Yes	$\forall \frac{\Delta x}{R}$	Yes	Yes	Yes

The \mathcal{C}^2 Wendland kernel is used with a ratio $R/\Delta x = 4$ (only 2D test cases are considered here). Finally, time derivatives are integrated using a 4th-order Runge-Kutta scheme.

1) *Riemann-based scheme derived from an ALE formalism*: Vila [18] derived a weakly-compressible Riemann-based SPH scheme written in ALE formalism. This scheme, then studied for instance in [12], is rewritten here using a velocity decomposition, leading to (15), where $\mathbf{u}_{ij} = \frac{\mathbf{u}_i + \mathbf{u}_j}{2}$, \mathbb{I} the identity matrix and \mathbf{g} the gravity. ρ_E , \mathbf{u}_E and P_E are the Riemann problem solutions at the interface between particles i and j which is supposed to be located at the $i-j$ mid-distance \mathbf{x}_{ij} and moving at the velocity $\mathbf{u}_{0ij} = \frac{\mathbf{u}_{0i} + \mathbf{u}_{0j}}{2}$ with $\mathbf{u}_0 = \mathbf{u} + \delta \mathbf{u}$. The MUSCL scheme with the minmod slope limiter is used to reconstruct the conservative variables $\begin{pmatrix} \rho \\ \rho \mathbf{u} \end{pmatrix}$ at \mathbf{x}_{ij} for an increased accuracy.

2) *Riemann-based scheme with PST velocity in the motion equation only*: The second SPH scheme studied in this paper was firstly derived by Parshikov & Medin [13] in a Lagrangian framework (i.e. without PST). In this scheme, the stabilization is also performed using a Riemann solver combined with MUSCL reconstructions.

Here, the PST is taken into account in the motion equation exclusively, leading to (16).

3) *δ -SPH scheme with PST velocity in the motion equation only*: The third SPH scheme used in this work is the δ -SPH scheme, firstly derived in [2], [7], and recalled in (17).

V. VALIDATION

This section aims at verifying the validity in 2D of the consistency property (5) studied theoretically in 1D so far. To this end, 2D Taylor-Green vortices for an inviscid flow are considered, the PST being crucial in this test case [1], [12]. The initial velocity and pressure are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} u_x^* &= \sin(2\pi x^*) \cos(2\pi y^*), \\ u_y^* &= -\cos(2\pi x^*) \sin(2\pi y^*), \\ p^* &= \frac{1}{2} [\cos(4\pi x^*) + \cos(4\pi y^*)], \end{aligned}$$

in the square shaped fluid domain of size $[0, L] \times [0, L]$. The superscript $*$ stands for the dimensionless variables with the reference length L , velocity U , time L/U and pressure $\frac{\rho U^2}{2}$, being U the maximum velocity in the initial condition. In this case, the nominal sound speed is taken as $c_0 = 10 \times U$.

Fig. 1 shows the time evolution of the maximum PST velocity $\|\delta \mathbf{u}\|_{max}$ for three different spatial resolutions and with the three SPH schemes tested. We observe that the property (5) is verified numerically for all the SPH schemes tested here.

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d\mathbf{x}_i}{dt} &= \mathbf{u}_i & + & \delta\mathbf{u}_i \\
\frac{dV_i}{dt} &= V_i \sum_{j \in \mathcal{D}_i} (\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j & + & V_i \sum_{j \in \mathcal{D}_i} (\delta\mathbf{u}_j - \delta\mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \\
\frac{d(V_i \rho_i)}{dt} &= -V_i \sum_{j \in \mathcal{D}_i} 2\rho_E (\mathbf{u}_E - \mathbf{u}_{ij}) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j & + & V_i \sum_{j \in \mathcal{D}_i} \rho_E (\delta\mathbf{u}_i + \delta\mathbf{u}_j) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \\
\frac{d(V_i \rho_i \mathbf{u}_i)}{dt} &= \underbrace{-V_i \sum_{j \in \mathcal{D}_i} 2[\rho_E \mathbf{u}_E \otimes (\mathbf{u}_E - \mathbf{u}_{ij}) + P_E \mathbb{I}] \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j}_{\text{Lagrangian part}} & + & \underbrace{V_i \sum_{j \in \mathcal{D}_i} [\rho_E \mathbf{u}_E \otimes (\delta\mathbf{u}_i + \delta\mathbf{u}_j)] \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j}_{\text{PST part}} \\
& & & + V_i \rho_i \mathbf{g}
\end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d\mathbf{x}_i}{dt} &= \mathbf{u}_i & + & \delta\mathbf{u}_i \\
\frac{dV_i}{dt} &= V_i \sum_{j \in \mathcal{D}_i} 2(\mathbf{u}_E - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j \\
\frac{d(V_i \rho_i)}{dt} &= 0 \\
\frac{d(V_i \rho_i \mathbf{u}_i)}{dt} &= \underbrace{-V_i \sum_{j \in \mathcal{D}_i} 2P_E \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j}_{\text{Lagrangian part}} & + & \underbrace{V_i \rho_i \mathbf{g}}_{\text{PST part}}
\end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d\mathbf{x}_i}{dt} &= \mathbf{u}_i & + & \delta\mathbf{u}_i \\
\frac{d\rho_i}{dt} &= -\rho_i \sum_{j \in \mathcal{D}_i} (\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j + \Pi_{i,\delta}^{(\rho)} \\
\frac{d(V_i \rho_i)}{dt} &= 0 \\
\rho_i \frac{d\mathbf{u}_i}{dt} &= \underbrace{\sum_{j \in \mathcal{D}_i} (P_i + P_j) \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j + \mathbf{\Pi}_{i,\delta}^{(\mathbf{u})}}_{\text{Lagrangian part}} & + & \underbrace{V_i \rho_i \mathbf{g}}_{\text{PST part}}
\end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

where the diffusive terms $\Pi_{i,\delta}^{(\rho)}$ and $\mathbf{\Pi}_{i,\delta}^{(\mathbf{u})}$ are:

$$\Pi_{i,\delta}^{(\rho)} = \delta h c_0 \sum_{j \in \mathcal{D}_i} \boldsymbol{\psi}_{ij} \cdot \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, \text{ with } \boldsymbol{\psi}_{ij} = 2(\rho_j - \rho_i) \frac{\mathbf{x}_{ij}}{\|\mathbf{x}_{ij}\|^2} - [\langle \nabla \rho \rangle_i^{\mathcal{L}} + \langle \nabla \rho \rangle_j^{\mathcal{L}}],$$

$$\mathbf{\Pi}_{i,\delta}^{(\mathbf{u})} = \alpha h c_0 \rho_0 \sum_{j \in \mathcal{D}_i} \pi_{ij} \nabla_i W_{ij} V_j, \text{ with } \pi_{ij} = \frac{(\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot (\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}_i)}{\|\mathbf{x}_{ij}\|^2},$$

with $\alpha = 0.01$ and $\delta = 0.1$ in the present work.

Figure 1: 2D Taylor-Green vortices. Top: time evolution of the maximum PST velocity $\|\delta u\|_{max}$ for three spatial resolutions. Left: Vila scheme. Middle: Parshikov & Medin scheme. Right: δ -SPH scheme. Bottom: convergence rate of $\|\delta u\|_{max}$ for the three SPH schemes tested.

Moreover, the theoretical first order of convergence is retrieved. In the left and center part of Fig. 2, the pressure field is plotted at $tU/L = 0.1$ and $tU/L = 1$ for the Vila scheme. While the initial configuration is Cartesian, we observe that the coherent structures start breaking from the very beginning of the simulation, and the PST introduced in this paper succeeds in suppressing all of them without altering the pressure field. In the right part of Fig. 2 we check the gain in the numerical dissipation provided by the PST, through the analysis of the kinetic energy decay. We observe that the dissipation tends towards zero while increasing the spatial resolution for the three schemes studied. Note that we aim here at showing that the PST has the same effect on the numerical diffusion whatever the SPH scheme used, and not to compare the diffusion properties of these schemes. For instance, the δ -SPH scheme would display a lower dissipation by using a smaller diffusion coefficient.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, Particle Shifting Techniques introduced in the SPH literature have been briefly recalled and analyzed and a specific attention has been paid to those based on Fick's law. Then,

conditions that should be verified by a PST (consistency of the PST velocity, Galilean and local rotation invariance, independence between local PST and global fluid flow) have been exposed. Using a theoretical demonstration in one dimension, it has been shown that using a PST based on Fick's law together with a characteristic velocity based on the Lagrangian velocity of the flow (local or global), as done in the literature, does not ensure the respect of such conditions. In order to recover theoretically these three conditions, using a relative velocity instead of the Lagrangian one is sufficient and a novel PST has been then derived. In addition, this novel PST has the advantage of being independent of the nominal sound speed, contrary to some PST proposed in the literature, providing it a natural compatibility (a priori) with the incompressible assumption.

This novel PST is not linked to a specific SPH scheme and the validation is performed with three different SPH schemes, all based on the weakly-compressible assumption. Note that the theoretical results of Quinlan *et al.* [14] are extended to the free-surface in [9], and the validation is then performed with both the presence of a free-surface and solid boundaries, modeled with the mov-

Figure 2: 2D Taylor-Green vortices. Left and center: Pressure field obtained with the Vila scheme and $L/\Delta x = 100$ at $tU/L = 0.1$ and $tU/L = 1$ respectively. Right: Kinetic energy decay for three spatial resolutions. Solid: Vila scheme. Dot-dashed: Parshikov & Medin scheme. Dashed: δ -SPH scheme.

ing ghost particle method and boundary integral method, in 2D and 3D. Since the paper [9] is under review, the results are available in [8], [17].

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